

RADAR MONITORING OF WETLAND HYDROLOGY: DYNAMIC INFORMATION FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

Megan W. Lang^a, Greg W. McCarty^a, Jerry C. Ritchie^a, Ali M. Sadeghi^a, W. Dean Hively^a, and S. Diane Eckles^b

^aUSDA-ARS, Remote Sensing and Hydrology Lab, Bldg 007, Rm 104, 10300 Baltimore Ave., Beltsville, MD 20705

^bUSDA-NRCS, Resource Inventory and Assessment Division, 5601 Sunnyside Ave., Beltsville, MD 20705

ABSTRACT

Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data can improve the ability to map and monitor forested wetlands. Forested wetland maps were developed using multiple incidence angle ENVISAT ASAR (C-HH) for the Tuckahoe River Watershed, Maryland. These maps were compared with U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service National Wetlands Inventory (NWI) and Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) Soil Survey Geographic Database (SSURGO) maps. Radar derived wetland maps and NWI maps showed a high level of agreement (88%). The radar derived wetland maps and SSURGO demonstrated a lower level of agreement (54%), primarily due to a greater estimate of hydric soils by SSURGO than forested wetlands by the SAR derived maps.

Index Terms— SAR, ENVISAT, wetland, hydrology

1. INTRODUCTION

Wetlands in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed are vital as they help to maintain water quality and aquatic habitat in one of the largest and most productive, yet threatened, estuarine ecosystem in the U.S. Wetland hydroperiod (i.e., temporal fluctuations in wetland inundation and soil moisture) controls wetland distribution and the biogeochemical processes (e.g., denitrification) that strongly influence the provision of wetland water quality services. Unfortunately, broad-scale forested wetland hydroperiod is difficult to monitor using ground-based and traditional optical remote sensing methods. However, the ability to accurately locate forested wetlands is vital to the management of wetlands in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed, where over half of all wetlands are forested. Satellite based radar data could improve the ability to map forested wetlands at a regional scale due to radar's ability to transmit energy through clouds and the forest canopy, the sensitivity of radar to key hydrologic variables [1] that control the distribution of wetlands, and the relative low expense and broad coverage that satellite based imagery provide. Although C-band SAR data have been used to map forested wetlands, the use of multiple incidence angle data for this application has received less attention. The use of multiple incidence angle data improves temporal resolution of map products, although it also complicates georegistration. Adequate

georegistration is especially challenging in areas of low topographic relief, like the Delmarva Peninsula, where microtopography can lead to the formation of numerous wetlands with complex boundaries. The goal of this research was to determine the feasibility of using C-HH SAR data collected at different incidence angles and look directions to map forested wetlands at the watershed scale.

2. BACKGROUND

The NWI produces wetland maps using interpretation of mid- to high altitude aerial photographs combined with field verification [2]. The NWI maps usually err less by commission and more by omission [3]. Forested wetlands are one of the most difficult types of wetlands to map using NWI's aerial photograph approach [3] and are therefore one of the most commonly omitted types of wetland. NWI maps are frequently out of date in areas undergoing rapid changes in wetland extent, such as the Mid-Atlantic Coastal Plain. Regardless of NWI's imperfections, NWI is one of the most commonly relied upon sources of wetland information in the U.S. [4].

Although not a wetland map, *per se*, NRCS produces SSURGO soils maps that can be used to locate wetland (i.e., hydric) soils. NRCS uses a combination of aerial photographs and field data to produce SSURGO. Although SSURGO maps are a reliable source of hydric soils data, the presence of hydric soils in SSURGO indicates both current and historic wetlands because historic wetlands usually retain their hydric soils status regardless of current hydrology.

Scattering and reflection of microwave energy are sensitive to variations in soil moisture and the presence/absence of surface water. C-HH band (~5.6 cm wavelength; energy transported with horizontal polarization from the sensor and horizontally polarized energy received at the sensor) energy is only partially attenuated by vegetation canopies in deciduous temperate forests [5], [6], which permits the monitoring of inundation and soil moisture below the forest canopy. Because greater canopy closure can decrease the amount of microwave energy which penetrates the forest canopy, the ability to use SAR data to detect hydrology below the forest canopy is greatest during the leaf-off season. Inundation greatly increases radar backscatter from forests. In the absence of inundation,

increases in soil moisture enhance the return of microwave energy [6], [7]. More detailed explanations of microwave scattering from forests can be found in [8] and [7].

3. METHODS

This study was conducted within the Choptank River Watershed, a tributary of the Chesapeake Bay, and focused primarily on the 398 km² Tuckahoe River Watershed, a sub-watershed of the Choptank. The 1756 km² Choptank River Watershed is located on the Delmarva Peninsula within the Coastal Plain Physiographic Province. The Choptank River delivers a significant amount of nutrients, primarily from agriculture, to the Chesapeake Bay [9]. The area is relatively flat (max elevation <30 m asl) and land cover is dominated by agriculture (~60%) with smaller amounts of forest and urban area [9]. A large percent of the land has been drained or otherwise hydrologically modified to accommodate agriculture, and hydrology is now difficult to infer using digital elevation maps.

NWI, SSURGO, and 2001 Multi-Resolution Land Characteristics Consortium (MRLC) National Land Cover Data (NLCD) maps were used in ArcGIS to investigate the amount and distribution of forests, wetlands, and hydric soils in the Tuckahoe River Watershed. Prior to analysis the SSURGO attribute file was edited to create a hydric soil column (hydric soil or non-hydric soil) using tabular data supplied by NRCS. NWI and SSURGO were used to determine the percent of forests (NLCD source) within the watershed which are considered wetlands or which have hydric soils using NWI or SSURGO, respectively.

A binary forested wetland map (forested wetland and other) was produced using multiple incidence angle ENVISAT ASAR (C-HH) data for the Tuckahoe River Watershed. Multiple incidence angle (i.e., average incidence angle of 19° [3-18-2006, ascending] and average incidence angle of 23° [3-02-2006, ascending and 3-27-06, descending]) images in both ascending and descending orbits were acquired from Eurimage. The ASAR data were delivered as precision, geocoded images. The images were automatically coregistered and stacked to form one image with multiple bands. A combination of median and enhanced lee filters with kernel sizes of 3 and 5 pixels were used to reduce speckle and smooth areas of the image with similar ground cover. A mask based on the National Land Cover Dataset tree canopy maps was applied to remove all areas with less than 39% tree canopy cover. A principal components analysis (PCA) of the multi-temporal SAR data was used to further reduce image speckle and isolate sources of temporal variation between SAR images. The first principal component (PC1) represented variations in image intensity associated with hydrology. PC1 was thresholded to create the binary forested wetland map. The threshold value used to create the binary map was selected because it best distinguished wetlands from uplands as

observed with field observations, fine-scale aerial photographs, and other supporting datasets. The binary forested wetland map was compared to NWI forested wetland and SSURGO hydric soil maps using ArcGIS. Before comparison, hydric soils were extracted from the SSURGO maps over forested areas using the NLCD 39% forest cover mask.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cropland dominates the Tuckahoe watershed (71%) but farmed lands are interspersed with smaller areas of forest (26%), often adjacent to or surrounding low order streams. The vast majority of wetlands mapped by NWI were found to be palustrine (92%), and most of these were forested (92%). The position (adjacent to agricultural fields) of these wetlands may make them well suited for intercepting agricultural run-off before it enters the Choptank River. Since hydric soils are usually still considered hydric long after their hydrology has been modified, the percent area of hydric soils in a watershed (39%) can provide a relative estimate of where wetlands were historically located. NWI, on the other hand, provides an estimate of the location of current wetlands (14% of the watershed). Therefore it is estimated that the Tuckahoe Watershed has lost over half of its wetlands. These statistics emphasize the importance of remaining wetlands and the need to best manage them.

A combination of the conservative nature of NWI's forested wetland maps, the inclusion of non-hydric soils within dominant hydric soil mapping units, and wetland loss may explain the disparity between the percentage of the watershed's forests that were found to have hydric soils (72% according to SSURGO) and the percentage which were found to be wetlands (44% according to NWI; Figure 1). Estimates of the extent of NWI's forested wetland omission errors vary widely [10], [4], but these errors can be significant. In addition, hydric soil units are classified based on the character of dominant soils and may have inclusions of non-hydric soils [4]. Some of the forests have been drained as evidenced by the presence of ditches and channelized streams (Figure 2). Although 71% of the Tuckahoe is currently used for agriculture, this area has been farmed for hundreds of years, and some areas that are currently forested were historically farmed. Other studies have found a wide range of percent agreement between wetlands as mapped by NWI and hydric soils as mapped by SSURGO (94%, [11]; 66%, [4]).

Although the two forested wetland maps (i.e., NWI and binary forested wetland map) agreed over 88% (82% negative agreement, 6% positive agreement) of their area, 12% disagreement was found. The 12% disagreement is not surprising considering the 25 years between the creation of the maps, the use of images from different years (with different weather conditions), and the use of different types of remotely sensed images and mapping techniques.

Figure 1: Maps of forested wetlands for the Tuckahoe River Watershed as depicted by the SAR binary forested wetland map (left) and NWI (center) accompanied by a map of hydric soils in forests (SSURGO, right). Note that overall correlation is high. The relatively large, linear area of forested wetlands that is not mapped by the SAR binary forested wetland map (see area marked by oval) is detailed below in figure 2.

Figure 2: Correspondence between forested wetlands as mapped by the SAR binary forested wetland map and NWI (left) and a false color NIR Quickbird image collected in April 2005. The two illustrations cover the same area. Note that the stream has been channelized to the northeast of the arrow leading to reduced inundation of the floodplain.

The 7% of the watershed area over which the binary forested wetland map found forested wetlands where NWI did not, may be attributed to the alteration of the landscape resulting in greater accumulations of water since the creation of the NWI map, NWI omission errors, and, in very limited circumstances, the presence of large metal structures beneath the forest canopy. A greater accumulation of water

may result from intended wetland restoration and redirection of water due to hydrologic alteration (e.g., beaver activity and drainage of fields into wetlands). Although estimates of NWI forested wetland omission errors vary greatly, they are well documented [3], [10], [4]. The correlation of C-HH SAR data with hydrology at a similar study site during the same time of year was found to be high, with the correlation between the radar signal and inundation resulting in a R^2 of 0.90 ($p < 0.001$) and the correlation between the radar signal and soil moisture resulting in an R^2 of 0.81 ($p < 0.001$; [6]). However, the radar signal is also known to be highly sensitive to metal and therefore the signal from a large piece of metal may be similar to that from a forested wetland. The 5% of forested wetlands that were mapped by NWI and not by the binary forested wetland map are most likely due to the loss of wetlands in the 25 years between the creation of NWI and the binary forested wetland map, although smaller portions of the discrepancy could be due to NWI commission errors or the inability of the radar to detect wetland due to greater canopy closure resulting in binary forested wetland map omission errors. A large area of suspected wetland loss can be viewed in Figures 1 and 2, with Figure 2 illustrating the relationship between the area of loss and a channelized portion of one of the Tuckahoe's tributaries (Mason Branch). A significant portion of the wetland ecosystem services formerly provided by floodplain wetlands adjacent to the now channelized stream are likely to be lost. Figure 3 illustrates the differences between NWI and the SAR derived wetland map and SSURGO and the SAR derived wetland map in more detail.

The SSURGO hydric soils maps (within forested areas) overlapped with forested wetlands according to the SAR binary maps 36% of the time, while 18% of the time the SSURGO and SAR maps found no hydric soils or wetlands (54% agreement). The SSURGO maps found hydric soils where the binary forested wetland maps did not 36% of the time, while the binary forested wetland maps found wetlands where the SSURGO maps did not find hydric soils about 10% of the time. The significantly greater estimate of hydric soils in forested areas by SSURGO as compared with radar derived estimates of forested wetlands is most likely due to the mapping of hydric soils by SSURGO in historic wetlands which no longer support wetland hydrology. The radar derived maps determine wetlands primarily based on the sensitivity of microwave energy to inundation and soil moisture; while SSURGO hydric soils are mapped based on soil features instead of current hydrology. The smaller area over which forested wetlands were mapped (radar) but hydric soils were not found is likely attributable to the grouping of hydric soil inclusions into larger non-hydric mapping units and commission errors of the radar derived maps. One explanation for possible commission errors includes the sensitivity of microwave energy to metal.

Figure 3: Comparisons between NWI and the SAR binary forested wetland map (left) and SSURGO and the SAR binary forested wetland map (right) for a small subset of the Tuckahoe Watershed.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The ability to map and monitor wetlands at an increased temporal resolution due to the inherent capabilities of SAR, the satellite platform, and the ability to integrate SAR data collected at multiple incidence angles and orbits offers a significant improvement over past wetland mapping and monitoring techniques. Although the use of radar data collected at multiple incidence angles and orbits may have contributed to inconsistencies between the radar derived map of forested wetlands and the NWI and SSURGO maps, these inconsistencies appeared to be small compared with other probable explanations (discussed above). Results are encouraging but further research is necessary to fully quantify the potential of multiple incidence angle and orbit SAR data for wetland mapping and monitoring. More current and accurate maps of wetland distribution and hydrology will improve estimates of wetland ecosystem services (e.g., pollutant reduction). Future research should include the comparison of radar derived estimates of wetland distribution and hydrology with measurements of denitrification and other biogeochemical processes.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Robert Tetrault, USDA Satellite Imagery Archive Manager, for providing the ENVISAT ASAR data used in this study and James Brewer and

Charles Hanner for providing SSURGO maps and soils related advice.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] L. Hess, J. Melack, and D. Simonett, "Radar detection of flooding beneath the forest canopy: a review," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 11, pp. 1313-1325, 1990.
- [2] Federal Geographic Data Committee, "Application of satellite data for mapping and monitoring wetlands - facts finding report: Technical Report 1," Wetlands Subcommittee, Federal Geographic Data Committee, Washington, D.C., 1992.
- [3] R. W. Tiner, "Use of high-altitude aerial photography for inventorying forested wetlands in the United States," *Forest Ecology and Management*, vol. 33, pp. 593-604, 1990.
- [4] G. M. Kudray and M. R. Gale, "Evaluation of national wetland inventory maps in a heavily forested region in the upper great lakes," *Wetlands*, vol. 20, pp. 581-587, 2000.
- [5] P. Townsend and S. Walsh, "Modeling floodplain inundation using an integrated GIS with radar and optical remote sensing," *Geomorphology*, vol. 2, pp. 295-312, 1998.
- [6] M. W. Lang and E. S. Kasischke, "Using C-band synthetic aperture radar data to monitor forested wetland hydrology in Maryland's Coastal Plain, USA," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 46, pp. 535-546, 2008.
- [7] Y. Wang, L. L. Hess, S. Filoso and J. M. Melack, "Understanding the radar backscattering from flooded and non-flooded Amazonian forests: Results from canopy backscatter modeling," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 324-332, 1995.
- [8] M. C. Dobson, F. T. Ulaby, L. E. Pierce, T. L. Sharik, K. M. Bergen, J. Kellndorfer, J. R. Kendra, E. Li, Y. C. Lin, A. Nashashibi, K. Sarabandi and P. Siquei, "Estimation of forest biophysical characteristics in Northern Michigan with SIR-C/X-S," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 877-895, 1995.
- [9] T. Fisher, J. Benitez, K. Lee and A. Sutton, "History of land cover change and biogeochemical impacts in the Choptank river basin in the mid-Atlantic region of the US," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 27, no. 17, pp. 3683-3703, 2006.
- [10] M. S. Rolband, "A comparison of wetland areas in northern Virginia: National Wetlands Inventory maps versus field delineated wetlands under the 1987 manual," *Wetland Journal*, vol. 7, pp. 10-14, 1995.
- [11] M. Kuzila, D. Rundquist, and J. Green. "Methods for estimating wetland loss - the rainbasin region of Nebraska," *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 441-446, 1991.